

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SOME QUESTIONS OF THE THEORY OF SOLUTION VISCOSITY

Yurov V.M.

*Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor
KarTU, Karaganda, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Zhangozin K.N.

*Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
TSK Vostok LLP, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Abstract

The article has a review on the viscosity models of liquids, starting with the viscosity models of past centuries, then models of viscosity of the XX century and, finally, the rheological models of the XX and XXI centuries. In the field of liquid rheology, there is no satisfactory quantitative theory that connects the rheological properties of the media with the parameters of their structure. The viscosity model of liquids is proposed, in which the liquid is considered as a system of non-current-appropriate molecules, immersed in a thermostat, which is the entire volume of fluid. Quantum transitions due to the interaction of molecules with a thermostat will be dissipative (with a probability P), in contrast to interaction with an external (for example, electric) field (with probability F). Dissipative processes lead to the fact that the secondary field Z_2 is always less than the primary Z_1 . Since the subsystem of molecules exchanges only energy with the thermostat, the corresponding ensemble of particles will be canonical. Theoretically calculated response function and a model is built. The fluid viscosity model that we proposed takes into account the thermodynamic properties of the liquid, its structure and response to external fields.

Keywords: visibility, liquid, molecule, model, dissipation, thermostat, Gibbs energy, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Today, solutions are distinguished as: Newtonian; Bingham viscoplastic; pseudoplastic; dilatant liquid. The classification of rheological models of liquids is carried out according to the dependence of the strain rate $\partial\tau/\partial t = \dot{\tau}$ on the shear rate (velocity gradient) $\dot{\tau} = \partial v/\partial z$. For a Newtonian fluid - a linear law: . For a non-Newtonian fluid: $\sigma = \alpha \dot{\tau}^n$. Pseudoplastic - $n < 1$, with slow movements the viscosity is high, then decreases. Dilatant liquid - $n > 1$, viscosity increases with increasing speed. Bingham plastic - the Bingham model is similar to the dry friction model:

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} \sigma_0 + \alpha \dot{\tau}, & \dot{\tau} > 0, \\ -\sigma_0 + \alpha \dot{\tau}, & \dot{\tau} < 0. \end{cases}$$

The most well-known pseudoplastic liquids are paints, emulsions and some suspensions. Although dilatant liquids are not so common, there are quite a lot of them, including most deflocculants: clay suspensions, sand/water systems. An example of a Bingham fluid is paint, in which, due to the action of binders (in particular carboxymethylcellulose), a threshold for shear stress arises, and it is capable of forming fixed layers on vertical surfaces. A separate case of non-Newtonian fluids are thixotropic and rheopex fluids, the viscosity of which changes over time. If the viscosity decreases over time, then the liquid is called thixotropic, and if, on the contrary, it increases, then it is

called rheopex.

In this article we will review models of liquid viscosity and propose our own model.

Viscosity models from past centuries

Newton's model

For the first time, internal friction (viscosity) between layers of liquid was noted by I. Newton in 1687. As I. Newton showed (1642-1727) [1], the force of internal friction is proportional to the velocity gradient and area of the contacting layers of the flowing liquid:

$$F = \eta \cdot \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta Z} \cdot S, \quad (1)$$

where η is the coefficient of dynamic viscosity.

This result is described in all encyclopedias, monographs and textbooks. However, Newton's errors are known when describing the rotational motion of a viscous fluid, which were later corrected by D. Bernoulli (1700-1782) and Stokes (1819-1903) [2]. A recent paper [3] states "that the viscosity of Newtonian fluids cannot depend on the shear rate." However, formula (1) has been used everywhere for more than 300 years (Fig. 1a).

Navier-Stokes and Poiseuille models

The equations of this model were derived by the French scientist Navier (1785-1836) in 1822 and the English scientist Stokes in 1845 and are called the Navier-Stokes equations (Fig. 1 b) [4]. The equations of motion of a viscous incompressible fluid will be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV_x}{dt} &= X - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 V_x}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V_x}{\partial z^2} \right) \\ \frac{dV_y}{dt} &= Y - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 V_y}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V_y}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V_y}{\partial z^2} \right) \\ \frac{dV_z}{dt} &= Z - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 V_z}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V_z}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V_z}{\partial z^2} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $\nu = \eta/\rho$ - kinematic viscosity of the liquid.

Figure 1. Viscosity models: according to Newton [1] (a); according to Navier-Stokes (b) [4]

Equations (2) are second order partial differential equations. In these equations, the density ρ , kinematic viscosity ν and projections of external mass forces X, Y, Z are known. Unknown quantities: pressure p and three projections of velocity V_x, V_y, V_z - a total of four unknowns. The number of unknowns exceeds the number of equations. The system of equations is not closed. One more equation is added to this system - the continuity equation. If we set the boundary conditions, then the system of equations (2) will have a unique solution, which, in the case of translational flow of an incompressible fluid in a channel with parallel walls in a gravity field (Fig. 1b), for the pressure loss Δp has the form:

$$p_1 - p_2 = \Delta p = \frac{3\eta \cdot \bar{V} \cdot l}{h^2} \tag{3}$$

The energy loss is proportional to the first degrees of viscosity η , the average speed $\bar{V}$ and the length l of the channel section under consideration. A similar method is used to solve the problem of laminar fluid flow in a round pipe with diameter d . For pressure loss we obtain Poiseuille's formula (1797-1869):

$$\Delta p = \frac{32\eta \cdot \bar{V} \cdot l}{d^2} \tag{4}$$

Maxwell's model

Initially, Maxwell's model (1831-1879) was proposed to describe the movement of highly viscous liquids, the periods of which are long compared to molecular times [5]. Maxwell's model can be represented by a purely viscous piston and a purely elastic spring connected in series, as shown in Fig. 2a. The model can be represented by the following equation:

$$\sigma + \frac{\eta}{E} \dot{\sigma} = \eta \dot{\epsilon} \tag{5}$$

Maxwell's model predicts that the stress σ decreases exponentially with time. This model can be applied to soft solids: thermoplastic polymers near their melting point, fresh concrete (ignoring its aging), and numerous metals near their melting point.

Kelvin-Voigt model

This model is named after the British physicist and engineer Lord Kelvin (1824-1907) and the German physicist Woldemar Voigt (1850-1919). The defining relation is expressed in the form of a first order linear differential equation [5]:

$$\sigma = E\epsilon + \eta \dot{\epsilon} \tag{6}$$

This model represents a solid body subject to reversible viscoelastic deformation (Fig. 2b). At constant stress (creep), the model is realistic; it predicts that the strain will tend to σ/E over time to infinity.

Figure 2. Viscosity models: Maxwell (a); according to Kelvin-Voigt (b) [5]

20th century viscosity models

Let's start with the review [6], which presents models proposed before 1940.

Frenkel model

As is known, Ya.I. Frenkel (1894-1952), when deriving the viscosity formula, proceeded from the idea of a liquid as a "spoiled" crystal lattice, in which atoms, having broken away from their places, moved into the "interlattice space" and oscillate around new unstable

equilibrium positions (Fig. 3a) [7]. The elementary flow process consists of the spontaneous movement of a particle from one temporary equilibrium position to another. Using the Stokes formula (assuming spherical particles, $f = 6\pi\eta a$), he obtains an equation for determining the viscosity coefficient η , namely:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{6\pi a} \cdot f = \frac{\tau_0}{a\delta^2} \cdot \frac{kT}{2\pi} \cdot e^{\frac{E_\eta}{kT}} \quad (7)$$

In the second version of the theory, the diffusion coefficient D is expressed according to the formula of Smoluchowski-Einstein and Ya.I. Frenkel receives:

$$\eta = B \cdot T \cdot e^{\frac{E_\eta}{kT}} \quad (8)$$

a)

This formula, as indicated by Ya.I. Frenkel, agrees worse with experiment than the exponential dependence of the form $\eta = A \exp(E_\eta/kT)$, which does not include the absolute temperature as a factor.

Andrade model

Andrade's formula (1887-1971) for the temperature dependence of viscosity is presented in general form:

$$\eta \cdot \nu^{\frac{1}{3}} = A \cdot e^{\frac{C}{\nu T}} \quad (9)$$

Formula (9) contains an exponential factor characterizing the energy relations of the process, as well as the specific volume. Testing this formula for different liquids gives very good agreement with experiment (Fig. 3b) [6].

b)

Figure 3. Viscosity models: according to Frenkel, solid molecules (on the left), and liquid molecules (on the right) [7] (a); according to Andrade [6] (b).

Khaikin model

In his theory of liquid viscosity S.E. Khaikin (1901-1968) uses Stewart's idea of the structure of liquids. Stewart (1828-1887) assumes that the liquid consists of small submicroscopic aggregates that retain a crystalline structure. The interaction of these aggregates, located in different layers of liquid, between which there is a velocity difference, leads to the emergence of a viscous force. Khaikin obtains, using Newton's formula, the following expression:

$$\eta = \frac{f_0 \cdot \sqrt{\rho} \cdot \Delta l^{\frac{5}{2}}}{8\sqrt{kT}} \quad (10)$$

Here Δl is the size of the aggregate, ρ is the density of the liquid, f_0 is the force acting on a unit surface, k and T are, as usual, Boltzmann's constant and absolute temperature.

Assuming then that the sizes of aggregates Δl are proportional to $(T-T_0)^{-1}$, and denoting all temperature-

independent coefficients through A , he obtains the following temperature dependence of viscosity for oils, alcohol, etc. [8] (Fig. 4a):

$$\eta = \frac{A}{\sqrt{T \cdot (T - T_0)^5}} \quad (11)$$

Bernal model

Bernal (1901-1971) derives an expression for viscosity:

$$\eta = A \cdot e^{\frac{B}{RT}} \quad (12)$$

In general, A and B are functions of temperature. The activation energy B , in addition, must also depend on pressure, since it significantly depends on the coordination of liquid molecules. Bernal divides all liquids into ionic, homeopolar, metallic and molecular (polymers) (Fig. 4b). In formula (12), parameter A is related to the molar mass of the polymer M [9].

a)

b)

Figure 4. Viscosity models: according to Khaikin [8] (a); according to Bernal [9] (b).

Eyring-Ewell model

The theory of liquid viscosity, developed by Eyring (1901-1981) and co-workers [6], like Bernal's theory, is based on certain ideas about the nature of the liquid state. Eyring approaches the question of the nature of liquids from the perspective of real gases and uses the methods of static mechanics. Eyring obtains the following formula for calculating viscosity at any temperature and pressure [6]:

$$\eta = 1.090 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{M^{1/2} \cdot T^{2/3}}{\nu^{5/3} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T}\right)_\eta} \cdot e^{\frac{\nu \cdot \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T}\right)_\eta}{nRT}} \quad (13)$$

The work of Mott and Gurney [10] is devoted to criticism of Eyring's theory of liquids, or more precisely to the derivation of the distribution function and entropy of melting according to Eyring, who, adhering to the main provisions of Bernal's theory, consider liquid as the limiting state of a polycrystalline body in which the difference between individual crystals disappears.

McLeod model

McLeod (1891-1977) gives an empirical formula for unassociated liquids:

$$\frac{\eta \nu^{1/3}}{\sqrt{T}} = \frac{B}{\nu - b}, \quad (14)$$

a)

where B is a constant, and for associated liquids:

$$\frac{\eta \nu^{1/3}}{\sqrt{T}} = \frac{B}{(\nu - b)^n}, \quad (15)$$

These formulas were tested by McLeod for organic liquids, and the agreement with experiment was no worse than Andrade's.

Einstein-Brinkman model

A special place in theoretical and applied rheology is occupied by Einstein's formula (1879-1955) for the viscosity η of dilute, unstructured colloidal solutions:

$$\eta = \eta_0 (1 + \alpha \varphi). \quad (16)$$

Here η₀ is the solvent viscosity, φ is the volume fraction of the dispersed phase in the suspension and α is a numerical coefficient equal to 2.5 for spherical particles. The formula gives results that are acceptable in terms of accuracy at a concentration φ of no more than 0.1 (Fig. 5a). In this case, it must be ensured that particles do not stick together.

Of the other forms, the Brinkman equation (1950-2011) is attractive for its simplicity:

$$\eta = \frac{\eta_0}{(1 - \varphi)^\alpha}, \quad (17)$$

which is derived based on Einstein's equation (16) and gives an obvious result: η = ∞ at φ = 1 (Fig. 5b), i.e. when transitioning to a monolithic solid.

b)

Figure 5. Dependence of the kinematic viscosity of an aqueous solution on the content of the solid fraction [11] (a); viscosity of colloidal solutions [12] (b).

Rheological models of the 20th and 21st centuries

In the field of rheology of liquids, there is not yet a satisfactory quantitative theory connecting the rheological properties of media with the parameters of their structure (see above). A huge number of rheological equations are mentioned in the literature; for example, in works [13-17] you can find information about more than 50 of their types.

Over the past 10 years, rheological models have been covered in doctoral and candidate dissertations [18-31]: viscoelastic properties of magnetic and electrical fluids; non-isothermal flows of two-phase non-Newtonian media over permeable surfaces; dynamics and disintegration of jets of complex liquids; dynamics

of an ultrathin layer of liquid; rheometric flows of polymer liquids taking into account shear stratification of the flow; rheokinetics of phase transformations of petroleum systems and gel-forming compositions; nonlinear behavior of concentrated polymer solutions under large periodic deformations; the influence of inertial forces on residual stresses and rheology of polymers and composites based on them; the influence of phase viscosity on the hydrodynamic characteristics of flows of immiscible liquids in microchannels of rectangular cross-section and much more. The same works provide a review of rheological models for all of the above problems.

Liquids, melts, dense plasma and a number of other connected systems that do not have an ordered structure are characterized by an unpleasant property

for constructing their theory - the average kinetic energy E per particle is equal in order of magnitude to the potential energy U [32]. Due to the lack of a small parameter for which it would be convenient to carry out decomposition, there is no strict theory as applied to liquids and melts, such as, for example, to a solid ($E/U \ll 1$) or gas ($E/U \gg 1$). In the 20th and 21st centuries, computer models replaced rigorous results [33, 34]. For example, Patent RU 2015611658 dated 02.20.2015 says: "The program is designed to calculate the activation energy of viscous flow and the pre-exponential of the Frenkel-Eyring-Arrhenius equation from two points, as well as to construct viscosity-temperature curves. The program is applicable for any liquids, solutions and dispersed media: polymers and their solutions, petroleum products, food media, etc." And quite a lot of such programs have appeared: Flow3D is a unique program for solving hydrodynamics problems. Developer: Flow Science, USA Developer website: www.flow3d.com; the GazKondNeft software system (PS GKN) performs the functions of computational modeling of phase transformations, thermophysical properties of gas and liquid mixtures, technological processes and schemes; "STARS" is a powerful modern software system that calculates the thermophysical properties and phase state of liquid and gaseous phases, oil fractions, mixtures, including mixtures of hydrocarbons with oil fractions, both at a single point and in a given range of temperatures and pressures; publications in the field of modeling the rheological properties of pulps showed that the most widespread among modern solutions are the following software systems: COMSOL Multiphysics, ANSYS Fluent, OpenFOAM, STAR-CCM+, NeNastran; The leading positions in the market of oil and gas simulation software products are currently occupied by the products of three foreign companies - Invensys Process Systems (which includes SimSci - Esscor, the owner of the PRO/II trademark), Aspen Technologies (with Hyprotech, the owner) brands HYSIM, HYSYS, Aspen) and ChemStations (which owns the CHEMCAD trademark).

Scientists from the Institute of Metallurgy of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences and the Ural Federal University developed in 2022 a method for theoretical high-precision determination of the viscosity of liquid metals using a trained artificial neural network. The practical application of artificial neural networks has become a symbol of the 21st century [35]. For example, in [36], a neural network approach was used to predict the viscosity and density of lubricating oils when gases are dissolved in them.

Our model

Our model is based on works [37-39], where solid bodies were considered. Let us now consider the liquid from this position. To measure any physical property of a liquid, you need to influence it with some primary field (magnetic, electric, etc.) and measure the secondary field (system response), the value of which carries information about the object. Since the process of interaction of an object with a field usually proceeds quite quickly (single-particle relaxation time is $\sim 10^{-12}$ s), it is clear that this process is far from equilibrium. On the other hand, the characteristics of the secondary field

carry information about an object that is in certain thermodynamic conditions and has thermodynamic parameters that are directly related to its structural, chemical and physical properties.

Thus, with the help of nonequilibrium statistical thermodynamics, it is possible to find a connection between the microscopic (quantum) processes of interaction of primary fields (the parameters of which can be controlled and varied within wide limits) with the macroscopic characteristics of the liquid.

Let us consider a liquid as a system of non-interacting molecules immersed in a thermostat, which represents the entire volume of the liquid. Quantum transitions caused by the interaction of molecules with a thermostat will be dissipative (with probability P) in contrast to interaction with an external (for example, electric) field (with probability F). Dissipative processes lead to the fact that the secondary field Z_2 is always less than the primary field Z_1 . Since the subsystem of molecules exchanges only energy with the thermostat, the corresponding ensemble of particles will be canonical [40]. Then the expression for statistical entropy has the form:

$$S = -k \sum_i f_i \ln f_i, \quad (18)$$

where f_i is the distribution function; k is Boltzmann's constant.

Differentiating (18) with respect to time and transforming, we obtain:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{k}{2} \sum_{i,j} (h f_i - \ln f_j) (P_{ij} f_i - P_{ji} f_j), \quad (19)$$

where P_{ij} is the probability of transition from initial i (with energy E_i) to excited state j (with energy E_j). For dissipative processes, the detailed equilibrium principle has the form:

$$\frac{g_i P_{ij}}{g_j P_{ji}} = e^{\frac{E_j - E_i}{kT}}, \quad (20)$$

where g_i, g_j are statistical weights for levels E_i and E_j . Then (19) will take the form:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{k}{2} P_{ij} \left(\ln f_i - \ln f_j \right) \left(f_i - \frac{g_i}{g_j} f_j e^{\frac{E_i - E_j}{kT}} \right), \quad (21)$$

Canonical distribution function [40]:

$$f_{ij} = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-E_{ij}/kT}, \quad (22)$$

where is the partition function:

$$Z = e^{-G/kT}, \quad (23)$$

where G is the Gibbs potential (free energy) of the thermostat + system of molecules.

Let us assume that the non-configurational part of the Gibbs potential depends linearly on the concentration N of molecules:

$$e^{-G/kT} = \sum_N h(N), \quad (24)$$

where $h(N) = \omega(N) \cdot e^{-G/kT}$; $\omega(N)$ - statistical weight.

After cumbersome but simple calculations, it is not difficult to show that the function $h(N)$ is a Gaussian distribution around the equilibrium value with small variance, i.e.:

$$h(N) = h(\bar{N})e^{-\Delta N^2/\bar{N}}. \quad (26)$$

Substituting (26) into (24), we have:

$$e^{-G/kT} = h(\bar{N}) \sum_{\Delta N} e^{-\Delta N^2/\bar{N}}. \quad (27)$$

To estimate the sum in (27), we replace it with the integral:

$$\sum_{\Delta N} e^{-\Delta N^2/\bar{N}} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2/\bar{N}} dx = \sqrt{\pi\bar{N}}.$$

Then (27) takes the form:

$$e^{-G/kT} = h(\bar{N})(\pi\bar{N})^{1/2}. \quad (28)$$

Using (24) and taking the logarithm of (28), we find:

$$G/kT = -\ln \omega(\bar{N}) + \frac{G(\bar{N})}{kT} + \frac{1}{2} \ln(\pi\bar{N}), \quad (29)$$

where $G(\bar{N})$ is the part of the total Gibbs potential associated with the concentration of molecules. From the estimate of the first logarithmic term it follows:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{k}{2} \sum_{i,j} P_{ij} e^{G^0/kT} e^{-\bar{N}} e^{-E_i/kT} \left(\frac{E_j - E_i}{kT} \right) \left(1 - \frac{g_i}{g_j} e^{2\frac{E_i - E_j}{kT}} \right). \quad (36)$$

Neglecting small terms and replacing the sum in (36) with an integral (which is true for a continuous spectrum of molecular energy values), we obtain:

$$P = \frac{2\Delta S}{k\tau} \exp\left\{-\frac{E_m - G^0/N}{kT}\right\}, \quad (37)$$

where ΔS is the change in entropy in the dissipative process; E_m is the average value of the energy of the ground state of molecules; τ – relaxation time.

For the response function Φ of the system to an external field we have:

$$\Phi = \frac{F}{F + P}, \quad (38)$$

where $F = 1/\tau$.

After transformations, we finally get:

$$\Phi = \frac{kT}{c} \cdot \frac{W}{G^0} \cdot \bar{N}. \quad (39)$$

$$\ln \omega(\bar{N}) = N \ln \left(1 + \frac{\bar{N}}{N} \right) + \bar{N} \ln \frac{N + \bar{N}}{N}. \quad (30)$$

Approximating the logarithm in the first term on the right side of (30) by the first term of its series expansion, and expressing the second term in terms of the Gibbs potential of the system of molecules G^f , we obtain:

$$\ln \omega(\bar{N}) = \bar{N} + \bar{N}G^f/kT. \quad (31)$$

Substituting (31) into (29) and neglecting the term $1/2 \ln(\pi\bar{N})$ compared to $\bar{N}$, we obtain:

$$G = G(\bar{N}) - \bar{N}G^f - \bar{N}kT. \quad (32)$$

As above, assuming that the thermodynamic potential depends on the equilibrium number of molecules G^f in a linear manner, i.e.:

$$G = G^0 + \bar{N}G^f, \quad (33)$$

where G^0 is the thermodynamic potential of the thermostat, we find:

$$G = G^0 - \bar{N}kT. \quad (34)$$

Using (34), expression (23) is transformed to the form:

$$Z = e^{-G^0/kT} e^{\bar{N}}. \quad (35)$$

Substituting (34) into (21), we find:

As a response function in [39], we take the kinematic viscosity ν , $NkT = PV = (V=1) = P$ – pressure in the liquid; W – kinetic energy of particles (molecules) of liquid $W = mv^2/2$; G^0 – Gibbs energy; $c = \text{const}$, m is the mass of particles, v is their speed. Equation (39) will take the form (Fig. 6a):

$$\nu = \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{p}{2G^0} \cdot mv^2. \quad (40)$$

Taking into account that $G^0 = \gamma S$, S is the area, we obtain the following equation for the relationship between the viscosity of a solution and its surface tension γ (Fig. 6b):

$$\nu = \frac{J}{\gamma}, \quad (41)$$

J – fluid constant under given thermodynamic conditions.

Figure 6.

Theoretical dependences of kinematic viscosity on pressure for some liquids (a), illustration of formula (41).

If the Gibbs energy is represented in the traditional form $G^0 = A + BT + CT^2$, then formula (40) takes the form (Fig. 7a):

$$\nu = \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{p}{2(A + BT + CT^2)} \cdot mv^2. \quad (42)$$

Figure 7. Theoretical dependence of the kinematic viscosity of a liquid on temperature (a), on the content of the solid fraction (b).

Figure 7b represents Einstein's formula (16) for the viscosity ν of dilute, unstructured colloidal solutions.

The kinematic viscosity coefficient ν is the ratio of the dynamic coefficient η to the density of the substance, i.e. $\nu = \eta/\rho$. All previous formulas are valid.

Our proposed model of liquid viscosity in the form (39) – (42) takes into account the thermodynamic properties of the liquid, its structure and response to external fields. For example, if a liquid is exposed to an electric field, then for most liquids it leads to a decrease in its surface tension γ . And this leads to an increase in the kinematic and dynamic coefficient of viscosity of the liquid according to formula (41), i.e. internal friction increases.

Conclusion

In this message, we touched upon the issue of liquid viscosity, which plays an important role in various industries, for example, chemical, petrochemical, food, glass, paint and varnish and others, where the initial and final products are subject to fluctuations in viscosity. Having an acceptable model of liquid viscosity, one can theoretically predict the synthesis of a particular final product. It is to this aspect that this article is intended.

This scientific article was published as part of grant funding for 2024-2026, IRN No. AR32488258 "Development of innovative technology for producing graphene by intercalating graphite with microcluster water and modifying HTSC ceramics with graphene" (the research is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan).

References

1. Newton I. Mathematical principles of natural philosophy. Ed. 4th. - Moscow, 2017. - pp. 486-488.
2. Mikhailov G.K. The formation of hydraulics and hydrodynamics in the works of St. Petersburg academicians (XVIII century) // Izv. Academy of Sciences of the USSR, MZhG, 1999, No. 6. - P. 7-25.
3. Mizerovsky L.N., Smimov P.R. Viscosity and internal friction in liquids // Russian Chemical Journal, 2020, V. LXIV, No. 1. - P. 1-12.
4. Batchelor J.K. Introduction to fluid dynamics. - M.: Research Center "Regular and Chaotic Dynamics", 2014. - 800 p.

5. Vorobyova E.V., Krutko N.P. Polymer complexes in aqueous and salt environments. - Minsk: Belarussian Science, 2010. - 175 p.
6. Leontyeva A.A. Modern theories of liquid viscosity // UFN, 1940, vol. 23, no. 2. - pp. 131–161.
7. Frenkel Ya.I. Kinetic theory of liquids. - Leningrad: Nauka, 1975. - 592 p.
8. Trucks and buses. Consumption of fuel, oil and technical fluids. - Moscow: Lights, 2017. - 192 p.
9. Zuev V.V., Uspenskaya M.V., Olekhovich A.O. Physics and chemistry of polymers. - St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University ITMO, 2010.-45p.
10. Mott N.F. and Gurney K.W. Note on the theory of liquids // Trans. Farad. Soc., 1939, Vol. 35. - P. 364-376.
11. Tursunbaeva A.K. Some questions of the theory of solution viscosity // Bulletin of KarSU, 2010, No. 4(60). - P. 60-67.
12. Gelfman M.I., Kovalevich O.V., Yustratov V.N. Colloidal chemistry. - St. Petersburg: "Lan", 2003. - 336 p.
13. Cheng D.C.-H. The art of coarse rheology // Brit. Soc. Rheol. Bull., 1989, Vol. 32, №16. - P. 1-15.
14. Craban S., Parzonka W., Havlik V. Non-Newtonian behavior of kaolin suspensions, in Progress and Trends in Rheology II. - N.Y.:Springer-Verlag, 1988. - 325 p.
15. Reher E.O., Haroske D., Kähler K. Strömungen nicht-Newtonscher Flüssigkeiten // Chem., 21 Jg., Heft 3., Marz., 1969. - S. 137-143.
16. Wildemuth C.R., Williams M.C. Viscosity of suspension modeled with a shear-dependent maximum packing fraction // Rheol. Acta., 1984, Vol. 23, №6. - P. 627-635.
17. Doraiswamy D., Mujumdar A.N., Tsao I., Beris A.N., Danforth S.C., Metzner A.B. The Cox-Merz rule extended: A rheological model for concentrated suspensions and other materials with a yield stress // J. Rheology, 1991, Vol. 35, №4. - P. 647-686.
18. Chirikov D.N. Viscoelastic properties of magnetic fluids. - Dissertation of the candidate in physics and mathematics. Sciences, Ekaterinburg, 2012. - 102p.
19. Chuprin V.A. Research and development of methods and means for monitoring the viscosity and density of liquid media using ultrasonic normal waves. - Dissertation of Doctor of Technical Sciences, Moscow, 2015. - 319 p.
20. Galimov R.A. Thin-layer nonisothermal flows of two-phase non-Newtonian media over permeable surfaces. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Kazan, 2015. - 152 p.
21. Shorstky I.A. Improving the process of extracting oilseeds based on the use of electrophysical influence. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Krasnodar, 2016. - 158 p.
22. Bazilevsky A.V. Dynamics and decay of jets of complex liquids. - Dissertation of Doctor of Physics and Mathematics. Sciences, Moscow, 2016. - 319 p.
23. Galechyan A.M. Percolation analysis of hysteresis of phase permeabilities during two-phase flow in oil reservoirs. - Dissertation of a candidate in physics and mathematics. Sciences, Moscow, 2018. - 92 p.
24. Lyushnin A.V. Dynamics of an ultrathin layer of liquid. - Dissertation of Doctor of Physics and Mathematics. Sciences, Perm, 2019. - 296 p.
25. Kuznetsova Yu.L. Rheometric flows of polymer liquids taking into account shear stratification of the flow. - Dissertation of a candidate in physics and mathematics. Sciences, Perm, 2019. - 123 p.
26. Kozhevnikov I.S. Rheokinetics of phase transformations of petroleum systems and gel-forming compositions. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Tomsk, 2019. - 102 p.
27. Cherpakova N.A. Nonlinear behavior of concentrated polymer solutions under large periodic deformations. - Dissertation of the candidate in physics and mathematics. Sciences, Tomsk, 2020. - 114 p.
28. Chechetov K.E. Aerodynamic method for measuring the surface tension of liquids. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Tambov, 2020. - 168 p.
29. Lesnyak L.I. The influence of inertial forces on residual stresses and rheology of polymers and composites based on them. - Dissertation of a candidate of technical sciences, Rostov-on-Don, 2021. - 119 p.
30. Mustakimov R.A. Film and gel-like materials based on interpolymer complexes of polysaccharides with functional synthetic polymers. - Dissertation of a candidate of chemical sciences, Ufa, 2022. - 158 p.
31. Kovalev A.V. The influence of phase viscosity on the hydrodynamic characteristics of immiscible liquid flows in microchannels of rectangular cross-section. - Dissertation of the candidate in physics and mathematics. Sciences, Novosibirsk, 2022. - 98 p.
32. Breg L., Nye J. Feynman lectures on physics. - M.: Mir, 1966, V. 7. - P. 275 - 287.
33. Korenchenko A.E. Methodology for studying the surface and rheological properties of liquids based on computer models. - Dissertation of Doctor of Physics and Mathematics. Sciences, - Chelyabinsk, 2008. - 212 p.
34. Shilov M.A., Veselov V.V. Computer modeling of molecular systems using the molecular dynamics method. - Ivanovo: IGTA, 2010. - 168 p.
35. Dudarov S. P., Papaev P. L. Theoretical foundations and practical application of artificial neural networks. - M.: RKhTU im. D. I. Mendeleeva, 2014.-104p.
36. Kolesnikov A.M., Mitrichev I.I. Neural network approach for predicting the viscosity and density of lubricating oils when gases are dissolved in them // Advances in chemistry and chemical technology, 2023, Vol. XXXVII, No. 4. - P. 10-12.
37. Portnov V.S., Yurov V.M. Relationship between the magnetic susceptibility of magnetite ores and thermodynamic parameters and iron content // News of universities. Mining Journal, No. 6, 2004. - pp. 122-127.
38. Yurov V.M., Eshchanov A.N., Sidorenko Yu.S. Nonequilibrium thermodynamics and radiolysis in solids // Bulletin of KarSU. Physics, 2005, No. 1(37). - P. 4-10.
39. Yurov V.M. Thermodynamics of luminescent substances // Bulletin of KarSU. Physics, 2005, No. 3(39). - pp. 13-19.
40. Kittel Ch. Statistical thermodynamics. - M.: Nauka, 1977. - 336 p.